

TRADITIONS AND INNOVATIONS IN MUSIC EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11254625>

Abstract: The article today cannot be limited to preserving traditions, it is necessary to develop them creatively. The interaction of traditions and innovations in musical education is considered from different points of view: as a concrete whole and as an autonomous sphere of society in its various relations with other spheres of economy and culture.

Key words: musical performance, musical culture, innovative activity, musical education, musical activity, traditions, innovation.

Introduction.

The centuries-old history of musical education has formed a unique system of training professional musicians and introducing the young generation to musical culture and creative activity, the content of which is based on the historical traditions of internal musical education and upbringing. In this regard, innovative processes and innovative activities that ensure the steady progressive development of musical education are of particular importance. Today, there is no unity in the interpretation of the concept of "innovative activity" in the scientific environment [4. 78-p].

Today, the strategic goal of political, economic and socio-cultural development of the country is to achieve the optimal level of development of Uzbekistan among the leading developed countries of the world. In this process, culture and art take a special place, in this context they acquire new qualitative characteristics and spiritual meanings. It seems relevant to understand such a field of culture and art as professional musical education. The reason for this is that musical education helps to develop human mental abilities and affect the mind through emotions, to form spiritual and moral values, humanistic outlook and outlook, sympathy and tolerance, developed aesthetic taste and creative activity.

In the context of music education, we believe that it can be understood as a purposeful and organized creative activity that includes various interrelated and interconnected types of work to achieve optimal results of music education. As part of innovative musical activities, technological innovations (introduction of new methods and technologies of musical and educational process implementation) can be distinguished:

- organizational innovations related to changes in the organizational structures of musical education;
- management innovations that define and change employee empowerment, culture and behavior.

For this, it is necessary to consider musical education as a certain whole and as an autonomous sector of the society in its various relations with other spheres of economy and culture. Such a multi-factorial approach allows defining and justifying the system of requirements and norms of modern music education and, on this basis, allows to identify innovations in music education and develop criteria for their evaluation. The purpose of our approach to this problem is to emphasize the role of traditions and the influence of innovations, as well as to determine the perspectives of musical education in the formation of a person of social and professional importance.

Modern requirements for the educational system have aroused interest in the active formation of issues of connection between the concepts of "innovation" and "tradition". In this context, the problem of interlinking and interpreting the concepts of "newness" and "innovation", "tradition" and "modernity" in educational activities has become one of the main issues. This is especially true in the field of musical education, which should take into account the interdependence and characteristics of the relationship between innovations and traditions in the development of musical culture. The relevance of the study of this problem is that, although innovation and tradition should be considered as two equal components of the musical education process, in practice their balance is constantly disturbed [1. p. 69].

Let's turn to the concept of "tradition". Translated from Latin, the word *traditio* means "tradition", "habit". The verb *tradere* - *transfere* is also actively used. This word means a material movement - the transfer of an object by one person to another. But gradually he began to reveal other intangible actions, for example, the transfer of certain skills and abilities. Currently, the term "tradition" is interpreted as various historical rituals, customs, ideas, skills of social and political activity, which are passed down from generation to generation and act as regulators of social relations. As for customs or cultural traditions in culture, this is the moral and aesthetic experience accumulated by certain peoples during the development period. These are skills and abilities developed by people in certain genres of folk art and later in art. In this context, the term "tradition" allows us to consider social relations from the point of view of culture and art.

Speaking about traditions in music education, it should be noted that they have always served as a basis for building educational activities, because they are the result of life experience. It is related to the interpretation of traditions as models of values and behavior that have been formed and changed throughout history, but remain the most stable and repeatable elements of socio-cultural experience. In modern music education, tradition should be understood as a method of legitimizing the norm by connecting it with the past. This is a special way to increase the norm.

In musical culture, it is very important to develop musical culture based on the social functions of traditions, which serve as the basis for preserving the collective experience of culture, the guarantee of the continuity of the forms of musical activity of people, and the traditional and innovative approaches. In the modern conditions of musical and educational activity, tradition remains one of the most important means of regulating this activity, but the mechanism of transmission of traditions has changed. Educators attach great educational value to traditions, but partially recognize their conservatism and emphasize that one should always pay attention to the past, where value was created, and not try to destroy it with a momentary whim (A. S. Makarenko).

It fully applies to musical education, which is carried out in centuries-old national traditions, which is repeated, stable and preserved, durable and long-term, sustainable. At the same time, on the one hand, it is necessary to emphasize the ambivalence of the tradition of musical education, which is relatively complete, but almost incomplete. They always have both conservative, stable old and constantly changing new things. A clear example of this is the thesis about the continuity of musical education, which has been interpreted and understood differently at different times, with an essential component that does not change. The content of pedagogical traditions in music education is heterogeneous. It reflects the pedagogical reality, stereotyped experience and results of musical activity, as well as the methods of defining them, which are reproduced from generation to generation. Thus, the pedagogical tradition regulates, organizes, coordinates the activities of all subjects of pedagogical reality.

The development of pedagogical traditions is a complex and uncertain process: "it is characterized by the dynamics of stages: the stages of birth, formation and disappearance. Passing through three stages of development, the tradition changes qualitatively: the old is replaced by a new one, and this leads to the replacement of the existing structure with a new formation (the process of

changing traditions). In the early stages of development, an active personal development of the invariant takes place, as a result of which different variants of it can appear and coexist" [5, page 54].

Music education and musical activity is a creative process: only creativity can lead us to success. But moving forward is possible only on the basis of previous positive experiences. The history of mankind has proved that today it is not limited to preserving traditions, it is necessary to develop them creatively: any tradition, if it develops creatively and meets the requirements of the time, leads to progress. Only a revision of the tradition leads to renewal and improvement of musical education.

The concepts of "innovation" should be distinguished. We understand innovation as a tool (a new method, methodology, program, etc.), and innovation as the process of mastering this tool. Innovation is a purposeful change, which should include new stable components in musical education, leading to the transition of the system to a higher level of development. As the innovation process in music education aims to change the main components of the existing education system, we draw key innovative ideas from our rich cultural past. As a process of implementing a certain innovation in social (musical and educational) practice, any innovation can be considered officially recognized (receives the status of innovation) if it is focused on the result and has invariable (traditional) features. Accordingly, the ratio of tradition and innovation can be expressed by the following formula: tradition is a way of repeating the norm, innovation is a way of changing the norm. Tradition can be understood as a mechanism of cultural continuity, and innovation as a mechanism of cultural development. They act as complementary and interacting phenomena. Thus, the pedagogical tradition is renewed, repeated, aged at the same time, that is, it has its own dynamics.

A clear example of this in music education can be a polyprogram of general music education. It appeared based on the concept of D. B. Kabalevsky [2. 45-p]. Many educational programs in the subject "Music" serve, on the one hand, as an indicator of the continuity of traditions, on the other hand - the aging of traditions, and on the third hand - an element of the development of the main ideas of the concept, i.e. an innovation that can be considered as an innovation, or as an analog innovation.

Conclusion.

Examples of important innovations in music education include recent advances in the use of information and media technologies. Tradition and innovation do

not exist outside of their interdependence. You should pay attention to the following words: "*everything is new - the old is forgotten.*" This trend is nowhere to be seen in music education. When it comes to musical learning, it's clear that everything old was once new, and methods, forms and tools that were once considered innovative have become traditional.

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